

KINETICS OF THE REACTION BETWEEN HEXAVALENT CHROMIUM AND OXALATE, CATALYSED BY MANGANOUS SULPHATE

BY DHIRENDRA NATH CHAKRAVARTY* AND SATYESHWAR GHOSH

The reaction between hexavalent chromium and oxalate has been specially studied in presence of manganous sulphate, which acts as a catalyst for the system. The temperature coefficient and the heat of activation for the catalysed reaction are calculated to be 2.932 and 19390 cal. respectively against the values 1.915 and 11995 cal. for the uncatalysed system. The order of the reaction in presence of manganous sulphate tends to become unimolecular whilst without manganous sulphate it appears as trimolecular. These results suggest a change in the reaction mechanism in the presence of bivalent manganese.

The reaction between oxalate and hexavalent chromium is very slow. Dhar (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 111, 707) showed the catalytic effect of hydrogen and bivalent manganese ions on this reaction velocity. According to him the order of this reaction in the presence of sulphuric acid is unusually high, being unimolecular with respect to chromic acid and trimolecular with respect to oxalate. Jablczynsky (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1908, 68, 38) postulated that the reduction of chromic acid by oxalic acid occurred in three stages, each one involving single electron change. Wagner (*ibid.*, 1928, 168, 279) also suggested the existence of intermediate products in the interaction of chromic acid and oxalic acid solutions. The reaction between chromic acid and oxalic acid therefore appears to be complicated. Further, the part played by bivalent manganese in this reaction, according to the literature available, is strange in the sense that while it is a catalyst in the oxidation of oxalate, it has a retarding influence in the oxidation of alcohol, as it will be seen from our further communications.

In the present paper we have investigated the order of this chemical change, specially in the presence of bivalent manganese. It should be mentioned here that previous workers investigated this reaction in high acid medium which considerably masked the effect of bivalent manganese. Hence, our investigations are limited to low hydrogen-ion concentration. The hexavalent chromium used in these experiments is from potassium dichromate and where the reaction is carried out in the presence of bivalent manganese, mixtures of oxalate and oxalic acid have been used so that the hydrogen-ion concentration is not high. In some cases, however, acid concentrations have been increased by adding dilute sulphuric acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

Reagents of A. R. quality were used and the solutions prepared in the double-distilled conductivity water. Standardisation of the solutions was done by the usual volumetric and gravimetric methods. The reaction rate was followed by the iodometric estimation of the total oxidant left over at different time intervals. The reaction

* Present address: Dept. of Chemistry, University of Utah, Salt Lake City, U.S.A.

mixtures were kept in a precision thermostat (Townson and Mercer Ltd.) kept in a temperature-controlled room so that the variation of the temperature between the bath and the room was $\pm 0.5^\circ$. Two Jena bottles, one containing the oxalate and the other dichromate (and manganous sulphate where required) were first kept in the bath. On attainment of the desired temperature these were mixed together and the time was noted. At different intervals of time 5 c.c. of the reaction mixture was pipetted out and poured in the acidified potassium iodide solution to estimate quantitatively the amount of oxidant left over at that time against a standard sodium thiosulphate solution. Readings for the non-catalysed and catalysed reactions are recorded below.

Kinetics Data for the Reaction between Hexavalent Chromium and Oxalate in the absence of Bivalent Manganese

In the following table, the values of the temperature coefficient and the heat of activation are compiled for the reaction between hexavalent chromium and oxalate, when it occurs in the absence of the catalyst, manganous sulphate.

TABLE I

Initial overall conc. of oxalic acid = 0.05 M.

Initial overall conc. of potassium dichromate = 0.0033 M.

Temp.	Velocity constants. $k \times 10^3$.	Temp. coef.		Heat of activation.	
		For 10° rise.	Mean.	For 10° rise.	Mean.
25°	4.115	1.875		11480 cals.	
30°	5.466	(25°-35°)	1.915	(25°-35°)	11995 cals.
35°	7.720	1.955		12510	
40°	10.690	(30°-40°)		(30°-40°)	

The average value of the temperature coefficient between 25° and 40° is calculated to be 1.915 for 10° rise and the average value of the heat of activation is approximately 12000 calories, a value which is sufficiently low. Experiments were also performed by regulating the concentrations of the reactants and for the above case when no manganous sulphate or sulphuric acid was used, the order was found to be 1 with respect to hexavalent chromium and 2 with respect to oxalate, and thus, the total order of the reaction was found to be 3.

Kinetics of the Reaction between Hexavalent Chromium and Oxalate in presence of Bivalent Manganese

The results of the catalytic effect of bivalent manganese on the reaction between hexavalent chromium and oxalate are presented below. Results parallel to those denoted in Table II are now put forward for the catalysed reaction.

TABLE II

Initial overall conc. of oxalic acid = 0.05 M.

Initial overall conc. of pot. dichromate = 0.0033 M.

Initial overall conc. of manganous sulphate = 0.00333 M.

Temp.	$k \times 10^3$.	Temp. coeff.		Heat of activation.	
		For 10° rise.	Mean.	For 10° rise.	Mean.
25°	11.71	3.077		20480 cals.	
30°	20.70	(25°-35°)	2.932	(25°-35°)	19890 cals.
35°	36.00	2.787		19300	
40°	57.70	(30°-40°)		(30°-40°)	

It is interesting to note here that the temperature coefficient of the catalysed reaction is higher than the temperature coefficient of the reaction when it is carried out in absence of bivalent manganese.

From the foregoing experiments, it is established that reaction between hexavalent chromium and oxalate is affected by the presence of manganous sulphate and acidity of the medium. In the following sections a thorough study was made on the order of reaction, calculated at various circumstances. The experimental procedure being similar, tables are only compiled for the different experiments performed.

Order of Reaction with Sulphuric Acid and without Manganous Sulphate

TABLE III

Overall conc. of $K_2Cr_2O_7$ = 0.0033 M and that of H_2SO_4 = 0.5 N. Temp. = 30°.

A. Potassium acid oxalate = 0.05 M.			B. Potassium acid oxalate = 0.1 M.		
Time.	0.1 N- $Na_2S_2O_3$.	$k \times 10^3$.	Time.	0.1 N- $Na_2S_2O_3$.	$k \times 10^3$.
2 mins.	3.70 c.c.	...	2 mins.	3.42 c.c.	...
10	3.26	15.83	5	2.80	66.63
20	2.72	17.09	9	2.00	71.03
25	2.54	16.36	12	1.72	68.74
30	2.32	16.67	15	1.40	61.02
35	2.14	16.60	20	1.02	67.22
40	1.98	16.45	23	0.82	69.19
Mean 16.46			Mean 67.30		

From the above table the order of the reaction is calculated to be 2.03, showing thereby again the bimolecular nature of the reaction with respect to oxalate. It is also shown from the velocity constants that the reaction becomes faster with the addition of sulphuric acid in the system.

Order of Reaction in presence of different amounts of Manganous Sulphate and without Sulphuric Acid

TABLE IV

Overall conc. of $K_2Cr_2O_7 = 0.0033 M$ and that of $MnSO_4 = 0.002 M$. Temp. = 30° .

A. Potassium acid oxalate. = 0.05 M.			B. Potassium acid oxalate. = 0.1 M.		
Time.	0.1 N- $Na_2S_2O_3$.	$k \times 10^3$.	Time.	0.1 N- $Na_2S_2O_3$.	$k \times 10^3$.
0 min.	8.73 c.c.	...	0 min.	8.76 c.c.	...
3	8.40	13.97	3	8.20	22.03
7	7.94	14.05	6	7.84	18.50
12	7.48	13.16	10	7.36	17.41
16	7.10	13.13	15	6.80	16.35
20	6.82	12.56	20	6.30	16.48
25	6.44	12.31	25	5.86	16.08
30	6.04	12.40	30	5.38	16.25
35	5.70	12.28	35	4.92	16.48
Mean 12.98			Mean 17.45		

TABLE V

Overall conc. of $K_2Cr_2O_7 = 0.0033 M$ and that of $MnSO_4 = 0.006 M$. Temp. = 30° .

A. Potassium acid oxalate = 0.05 M.			B. Potassium acid oxalate = 0.1 M.		
Time.	0.1 N- $Na_2S_2O_3$.	$k \times 10^3$.	Time.	0.1 N- $Na_2S_2O_3$.	$k \times 10^3$.
0 min.	8.76 c.c.	...	0 min.	8.76 c.c.	...
3	7.80	38.68	3	7.52	50.89
7	6.74	37.30	7	6.54	43.95
11	5.84	36.87	11	5.48	42.47
15	5.00	37.38	15	4.54	43.72
20	4.20	36.72	20	3.60	44.47
25	3.46	37.16	25	2.80	45.63
30	2.80	38.02	30	2.24	45.50
35	2.30	38.21	35	1.70	46.85
Mean 37.54			Mean 45.43		

In presence of manganous sulphate of final concentration 0.002 M, the order of the reaction is found out to be equal to 0.43 with respect to oxalate. When more of manganous sulphate is added, e.g. of final strength 0.006 M, the order with respect to oxalate goes down to 0.27, and thus, the total order tends to unity.

Order of Reaction in presence of both Manganous Sulphate and Sulphuric Acid

TABLE VI

Overall conc. of $K_2Cr_2O_7 = 0.0033 M$ and that of $MnSO_4 = 0.002 M$ and of $H_2SO_4 = 0.5 N$. Temp. = 30° .

A. Potassium acid oxalate = 0.05 M.			B. Potassium acid oxalate = 0.1 M.		
Time.	0.1 N- $Na_2S_2O_3$.	$k \times 10^3$.	Time.	0.1 N- $Na_2S_2O_3$.	$k \times 10^3$.
2 mins.	3.60 c.c.	...	* 2 mins.	3.26 c.c.	...
7	2.60	65.56	4	2.50	132.76
10	2.08	68.56	6	1.84	143.01
13	1.70	68.23	8	1.30	136.60
15	1.48	68.37	11	0.88	145.52
18	1.20	68.78	13	0.60	153.90
Mean 67.78			15	0.34	150.67
			Mean 143.74		

The order for the above set is calculated to be 1.07 with respect to oxalate. Thus, the total order becomes equal to 2. This value for the order of reaction in presence of sulphuric acid shows that the catalytic effect of manganous sulphate is minimised in presence of sulphuric acid in the system, which is obvious because of the fact that sulphuric acid itself enhances the reaction.

Generally a reaction with lower value of activation energy for a chemical reaction leads to its greater velocity at ordinary temperatures. But it is noted from Tables I and II that though the rate of oxidation of oxalate by hexavalent chromium is considerably increased in presence of manganous sulphate, yet there is a considerable increase in the reaction velocity. The velocity constant of a reaction can be represented by (cf. Theory of Absolute Reaction Rate) :

$$k_r = (kT/h) \cdot e^{\frac{\Delta S^\ddagger}{R}} \cdot e^{-\frac{E_a}{RT}}$$

where $\Delta S^\ddagger$ is the entropy of activation, E_a is the heat of activation, and k_r , the velocity constant.

From the above expression we find that the value of k_r is dependent on the value of $\Delta S^\ddagger$ and E_a . It appears therefore that the value $\Delta S^\ddagger$ is highly increased in the presence of manganous sulphate, so much so that the velocity of the reaction becomes large, though the heat of activation is also increased. This indicates that the reaction mechanism of the oxidation of oxalate by hexavalent chromium involves different species of ions than those reacting in the absence of bivalent manganese (cf. Frost and Pearson, "Kinetics and Mechanisms", John Wiley and Sons, Inc., 1952).

C O N C L U S I O N

From the experimental observations presented in this paper on the reaction between hexavalent chromium and oxalate, the following salient features may be noted :

1. The oxidation of oxalate by hexavalent chromium is unimolecular with respect to the latter, but the order with respect to the former considerably changes as the reaction is catalysed by the acid or by bivalent manganese.
2. In presence of sulphuric acid the order with respect to oxalate is 2 or even 3, but it has a tendency to fall down to zero with increasing concentration of bivalent manganese. Thus, a changed mechanism of the reaction, when occurring in presence of manganous sulphate, is expected.
3. The temperature coefficient and the heat of activation also lead to the similar conclusion. The rule of Dhar (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1923, 128, 218) that greater the order of chemical reaction, smaller the temperature coefficient, has been found to be true.

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REVIEWS

Fundamentals of Chromatography.—By Harold G. Cassidy. Vol. X of the Weissberger Series: Technique of Organic Chemistry. Published by Interscience Publishers Inc., New York, 1957. Pp. 447 + xvii. Price \$ 9.75.

The volume under review, as explained in the preface by the Editor, is the outcome of an attempt to revise the Chapters on Chromatography which appeared in Vol. V of the Weissberger Series under the caption "Adsorption and Chromatography". The author explains in his preface the reasons for a new book on chromatography alone written from a new point of view.

Chromatography with its varied offshoots has become a formidable tool in the hands of chemists. As it often happens, the practice and technique become much more familiar than the principles involved. This remark is especially pertinent to the technique of chromatography. A critical appreciation of the theories and principles formulated by different workers has not been forthcoming. Chapter IV on General Theory fills up this inadequacy by providing a connected account of the broad principles in a simple manner, leaving out the intricacies. For those who are interested in a general outline of the principles of chromatography, this account is excellent. It also brings out clearly how a general principle runs through the apparently different procedures.

The plan of dividing each chapter dealing with a particular technique into principles, classification, apparatus, procedures and modifications together with copious examples of applications shows the cautious effort of the author to make the book highly useful to its readers. There are numerous practical hints, meant primarily for actual workers, about the different techniques discussed in the separate chapters, but chapters XII-XV dealing with recognising and evaluating zones, relation of R_{aud} R_{f} to molecular structure, choice of mobile and stationary phases and a systematic scheme of chromatographic separation show the meticulous care with which the book has been prepared. In fact, one hardly misses the author's careful planning of the book and the desire to make it sufficiently helpful. Chapter XIII on the relation of R_{aud} R_{f} to molecular structure is likely to evince further interest along this line.

The sources of chromatographic equipment, addresses of industrial firms dealing with chromatography in one form or the other, listed in the appendix, and the list of up-to-date references numbering more than one thousand, carefully compiled by the author, are some of the other attractive features of the book.

S.K.M.

Vitamins and Hormones.—Edited by Robert S. Marris, G. F. Marian and Kenneth V. Thimann. Vol. XIV. Pp. 486 + xi. Published by Academic Press Inc. Publishers, New York, 1956.

The present volume is in series of annual publications on the recent advances in vitamin and hormone researches. It has maintained the high standard and tradition of

its predecessors. Its contributors are all eminent workers in their respective fields. The first two chapters deal with vitamins—one relates to the intestinal synthesis of vitamins in nonruminants and its importance in the nutrition of the host, and the other article discusses some aspects of vitamin-A metabolism. Large amounts of many vitamins are synthesised by the bacteria inhabiting the intestinal tract of animals. In the case of nonruminants, only a few vitamins are utilised by direct absorption unlike in the case of ruminants where the requirement for water-soluble vitamins is almost fully satisfied from the intestinal synthesis. Not much work has been done so far to determine which of the specific requirements for vitamins are satisfied by intestinal synthesis in human being. There is a suggestive evidence that many adults secure a part of their pyridoxine and vitamin B₁₂ from this source. The author has also reviewed the work of the effect of antimicrobial compounds, including antibiotics on the intestinal microflora and its influence on the nutrition of the animal. It seems that though some growth promoting effects are observed in certain cases on administration of antimicrobial compounds, the exact mechanism of the change that is brought about is not known.

In the vitamin-A metabolism, the author points out that although much progress has been made in describing the deficiency syndrome and the effect of vitamin A on visual process, its mode of action in promoting the growth and maintaining the usual status in the body is considered obscure. The site and mechanism of synthesis are described in details, particularly the latest work of Glove and Redfearn who suggest that the initial attack on β -carotene occurs at the end of the molecule and proceeds by β -oxidation until retinene is formed, reduced to vitamin A and finally absorbed. Then the mode of action of vitamin A on protein and amino-acid metabolism, hormonal action, particularly pituitary adrenal function, oxidative mechanism, hyperkeratosis, as far as they are known up to the present, are described. The authors feel that the vitamin has its own peculiar mode of action which must not be studied in isolation.

In the two chapters on the hormonal control of carbohydrate metabolism, the first deals with the effect of hormones at different sites of carbohydrate metabolism - muscle, liver, kidney, brain, retina etc. It helps one to get in a single article all the available information on the behaviour of different tissues during carbohydrate metabolism and how it is regulated under normal and abnormal conditions. The next article describes the syndrome of diabetes mellitus, occurring clinically and produced experimentally not primarily due to lack of insulin. Thus pituitary hyperglycemias, adrenal hyperglycemias, pancreatic hyperglycemias, renal, thyroid and estrogenic hyperglycemias are all described giving their particular features and the over-all relation to each other. It is quite interesting to observe that although secretions from every endocrine gland are associated with hyperglycemia, only insulin is always hypoglycemic.

Biochemical studies on insect hormones is probably the first of a detailed review on the subject and biochemists and zoologists alike would find it highly stimulating. As in the case of vertebrates, the insects also have a highly developed system of endocrine glands. The principle of a dominant hormone, as we know from the hypophyses of vertebrates, has its counterpart in neurosecretory cells of insects. The morphogenesis of insects can also be followed with the hormonal regulation of development. The biological basis of the hormones is, however, incompletely understood.

The other articles deal successively with glucoronide metabolism, bioassay of gonadotropins and microbiological transformation of steroids. Whereas the enzyme β -glucoronidase is present widely in the animal body and participates in the hydrolysis of naturally occurring glucoronides of steroid, and nonsteroid alcohols and phenols, the enzyme-synthesising conjugated glucoronides from glycogen and aglycones are present only in liver and kidney. It is still not known whether the same synthetic system is involved in the production of chondroitin and hyaluronic acid.

The increasing importance of steroids in clinical use has heightened interest in their synthesis and interconversion by different means, the most interesting being those brought about by micro-organisms. The article provides a list of the number of steroidal transformations brought about by a large number of micro-organisms, some of which have been commercially exploited as in the case of antibiotics manufacture. The technique of paper chromatography has once again come to be particularly useful in the detection and studies of the microbial changes of steroids. General description is given of the fermentation processes and the isolation methods, and the reader is referred to other articles of interest dealing with the subject.

All the chapters have at their ends quite a comprehensive list of references. At the end of the book there are also author and subject indexes. The book as a whole will be widely appreciated by all workers in the field of vitamin and hormone research and is an extremely useful addition to the recent publications on this particular field of Biochemistry.

S. G. & S. C. R.

Synthetic Polypeptides.—By C. H. Bamford, A. Elliot and W. E. Hanby. Published by Academic Press Inc. Publishers, New York, 1956. Pp. 445 + xiii.

In this period of rapid scientific progress, there are two opposing demands for scientific literature. On the one hand, there is always the demand for a comprehensive treatise on a given subject for specialists working in it. On the other, there is also a demand for a concise summary of the subject for those who wish to keep pace with progress outside their particular field. Then again, there are certain border-line subjects which are of interest to chemists and physicists as well. Books on those subjects are written for one class of workers or other and special emphasis is laid either on the physical or on the chemical aspect of the problem.

Synthetic polypeptides form one such border-line subject, but Bamford, Elliot and Hanby's book is one written for those interested in the subject of proteins in general and polypeptides in particular, irrespective of their faith and belief. Thus organic chemists will find in this book a thorough and up-to-date review of the various methods of preparation of synthetic polypeptides and the probable mechanism involved in their formation; the physical chemists will find what is probably the best account of the physico-chemical methods used in the detection of the presence of hydrogen bonds and the role of such bonding in determining the characteristic properties of these compounds, and the physicists will find their X-ray diffraction techniques in action in a complex field.

To some it may appear that rather too much stress has been laid on the role of hydrogen bonding, but the reviewer feels that the importance of hydrogen bonding in these systems cannot be overestimated and the authors have done proper justice to the whole subject, although what exactly is the nature of these bonds and what type of interactions are involved in these bond formation have not been clearly explained. The book contains one chapter on Silk protein which according to reviewer is the best account of the physico-chemical aspects of silk fibroin existing in chemical literature.

The book is unquestionably a remarkable achievement, presenting a wealth of information in an eminently readable form. As a general review it is certainly unsurpassed, but its standard will greatly limit the number of general readers, who will wish to read it through. The experts, on the other hand, will find it sufficiently detailed to be helpful in his own subject, be it organic chemistry, physical chemistry or physics. Workers in one particular field can benefit by dipping into other sections to see what their fellow workers are doing and in so doing may well find fresh ideas.

There is one great defect in this book which the reviewer considers his duty to point out. The book contains no authors index. Let us hope that this will be included in the next printing. S. B.

Dictionary of Organic Compounds: 4 Volumes.—By Prof. Sir Ian Heilbron, D. Sc., LL. D., F.R.I.C., F.R.S. and H. M. Bunbury, M. Sc., F.R.I.C. Published by Eyre & Spottiswoode, 15 Bedford Street, London W C. 2, 1953. Price £ 7/-each.

Heilbron's "Dictionary of Organic Compounds" was first published during the period 1934 and 1937, in three volumes and it gained enormous popularity among the research workers interested in organic compounds. The second edition of the book appeared in November 1953 in four volumes.

In this new edition not only over 2500 new entries are included but also some thousands of additions or amendments have been made to the previous entries. Important recent references have been incorporated in many cases and in some cases references of research work of 1953 have also been included. The mode of presentation in the new edition remains the same as in the previous edition. Due to the inclusion of a large number of compounds the Dictionary has become a standard reference book.

In each short monograph molecular and structural formulae, physico-chemical properties, functional derivatives and important references covering various informations regarding the compounds are given. The authors deserve thanks for their effort in revising the Dictionary. B.P.

Advances in Carbohydrate Chemistry: Vol. XI.—Edited by Melville L. Wolfram. Published by the Academic Press Inc. Publishers, New York, 1956, 465 + vii pages. Price \$ 11.00.

The present volume is uniform in standard with its preceding ten volumes. Its contributors have been selected from several countries—England, Scotland, Canada, Spain and the United States to bring close together contemporary research workers in different fields of carbohydrates. The specialised articles on Pericdate oxidation of carbohydrates by J. M. Bobbitt, the Osazones by S. Bayne and J. A. Fewster, Reactions of monosaccharides with β -ketonic esters and related substances by F. Garcia Gonzalez, Kojic acid by A. Beellk, Biosynthesis of monosaccharides by L. Hough, Branched-

chain sugars of natural occurrence by F. Shafizadeh, Nucleic acids by Barker, and Aspects of the physical chemistry of starch by C. T. Greenwood are indispensable to serious students of carbohydrate chemistry. The chapters on periodate oxidation of carbohydrates and kojic acid are the most interesting reading for students and teachers of organic and bio-chemistry whose special study is not exactly carbohydrates.

R. C.

Introduction to Physical Chemistry : Vol. I.—By S. N. Mukherjee, D. Sc., Professor of Physical Chemistry, Jadavpur University. Published by Art Union, Calcutta, 427 pages.

This is a well-written book for the students who want a clearⁿ introduction to principles of Physical Chemistry. It will certainly be a useful book for the Honours and Post Graduate students of our University and the teachers also will be gratified to see this introductory text.

In the first volume the author has included seventeen chapters covering the kinetic theory of matter, the two laws of thermodynamics, liquid and solid states of aggregation and the properties of solutions. The treatment is quite lucid and yet every topic has been developed from mathematical stand-point. The work reflects the experience of a seasoned teacher. Many cases, where the beginners are likely to be confused, have been specially explained and developed. The treatment of the Van der Waal's equation or coefficient of viscosity will bear this out.

One special and a very good feature of the book is that the author has throughout been very careful to impress upon the readers the necessity of use of proper units. The well-chosen problems at the end of the chapter will be appreciated by students. The chapters II and III could, however, be condensed considerably. The treatment of the 'solid state of aggregation' should have been a little more elaborate. In comparison to other chapters this has been very much compressed. The simple applications of the laws of thermodynamics have been nicely illustrated but the discussion on some more statements of the second law other than those of Clausius and Kelvin would be appreciated. The author mentions only, "Many special statements of this law can be made". There are, however, quite a number of printing mistakes, which it is hoped, will disappear in its next publication.

Altogether the book is a nice presentation of the fundamental principles of Chemistry that will stimulate the knowledge-hungry students. Even a moderately bright student with some knowledge of calculus will find this book an excellent diet indeed.

P. C. R.

Commercial Waxes.—Edited by H. Bannett. Published by the Chemical Publishing Co. Inc., N.Y., U.S.A., pp. 688. Price \$ 15.00.

The book under review is the enlarged and revised edition of the original one. It deals with both natural and synthetic commercial waxes. The physical and chemical properties of these waxes and their mixtures and solutions have been recorded in tabulated forms. These are generally not available in detail. The chapter on analysis, identification, detection of adulteration provides an additional interest. The chapters on uses and formulary, respectively will be of interest to the expert as well as to a beginner.

There are some printing lapses which are expected to be removed, e.g. page 277 figure 53, instead of % paraffin it should be specific gravity.

A. N. S.

Physical Methods in Chemical Analysis: Vol. III.—Edited by Dr. Walter G. Berl. Published by Academic Press Inc. Publishers. New York, 1956. Pp. 652 + xii. Price \$ 13.50.

Review articles such as those that are presented in the present series, serve several useful purposes. One of these is the information they convey particularly to the chemist of physical tools which he can use with great advantage for his research and routine work. The adaptation of physical techniques to analytical purposes is taking place so rapidly that the chemist cannot remain satisfied without equipping himself with the latest improvements and new innovations. The development of the techniques is the outcome of a constant need for more and more accurate, rapid and sensitive methods which would unravel the details not only on a macro level but also on a molecular level. The techniques are often quite complicated and their principles, more so. Thanks to the manufacturing firms, most of the physical tools are now available in almost fool-proof condition. But even then for the interpretation of results or for adaptation to a different set of experiments, a sound knowledge of the theoretical principles as well as the constructional intricacies is essential. The object of the book is to render a useful service to the chemists, and hence, the articles although written by specialists are not meant for the specialists alone. The treatment of each is according to a more or less general plan: introduction; theory; apparatus & techniques; modifications, if any. Applications and a full reference to earlier and recent work up to 1956, appropriate illustrations, practical hints, reference to and description of available equipments and particularly the scope and limitation concerning each apparatus and method are important features of the book.

Some of the articles, as one can see, supplement and extend very effectively the scope of those published in Volumes I and II and thereby the desirable link between the three volumes has been maintained. Some of the techniques, viz., field ion microscopy and neutron activation, although not yet within the compass of every-day use, are destined, as the Editor puts it, to open up "regions of versatility and sensitivity of detection unmatched by any other techniques." By bringing out this and the previous two volumes of this series, Dr. Berl has rendered a very useful service to the practising chemists and students of advanced instrumentation. The established reputation of the Publishers has been maintained throughout the book.

S. K. M.

